

A simple and fast single step method to isolate and stain the CD27 B cells (plasma cells) with quantum dots magnetic beads antibody conjugate for fluorescent microscopy

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Aim. The staining of mononuclear cells is done in two step process today with conventional dyes. These are isolation in first step and afterwards staining in second step; hence this two-step process takes a lot of time till one can observe the cells under fluorescent microscope. Moreover, quantum dots have other advantages against the conventional dyes like FITC, Cy3, Cy5 etc. as they do not bleach and they emit the fluorescence in narrow range. We decided to develop a new method, where one can isolate and stain the cells in one step with quantum dots magnetic beads antibodies conjugate for CD27 positive B cells as example.

Methods. CD27 positive cells from immunized mononuclear cell cultures were stained and isolated in magnetic racks with quantum dot magnetic bead antibody conjugate with two different wavelengths 510 and 700 nm in one step. After that they were fixed on slides and observed under fluorescent microscope.

Results. It was found that in all 10 experiments, the CD27 positive cells (plasma cells) were stained successfully and they emitted specific fluorescence under microscope, hence only CD27 specific cells were observed and there were no other cells. Under the normal microscope, CD27 positive cells were observed because the magnetic beads were attached to their surface. Isolation and staining steps were finished within 30 minutes.

Conclusions. This may be a first report in literature about the successful development of a fast and single step method to isolate and stain the CD27 B cells from immunized mononuclear cells with quantum dots magnetic beads antibody conjugate within 30 minutes against the two-step method, which takes more than one hour to be finished. Moreover, quantum dots gave bright fluorescence on the surface of CD27 B-cells.

Keywords: CD27 B cells, plasma cells, quantum dots magnetic beads antibody conjugate, immune response.

Quantum dots are new generation of staining agents for different cells as they are being used for flow cytometry as well as advanced fluorescent microscopes like confocal fluorescent microscopy. The quantum dots have a number of advantages against the commonly used staining agents like FITC, PE, Cy3, Cy5 and so on because they do not fade away after the staining. Moreover, they have very narrow range of emitting fluorescent because the conventional dyes have the problem of cross talking [1-7].

Magnetic beads are being used in biomedical field for last many years. They are also being used to isolate the different cells like T-, B-cells, stem cells as well as developments of different assays worldwide [8-12].

In daily use, many laboratories are using two step methods to isolate and stain the cells for flow cytometry as well as other fluorescent methods. User usually does the lysis of erythrocytes in a lysis buffer from blood or bone marrow biopsies and after that there are washing steps following the centrifugation in the first step. At the end, the staining with different conjugated antibodies is done. Now a days such antibodies are available commercially [13-14]. After that they are observed under the fluorescent microscope. These are two essential steps, which are needed to conduct the fluorescence studies. Moreover, these conventional dyes have disadvantages e.g., they emit signals in other channels known as cross talking and making it difficult to analyze fluorescence particularly in the multiplex assays and they fade away quickly. Quantum dots have advantages: they emit signals in narrow width, therefore there is almost no cross talking and they do not fade away; hence these samples can be stored for long term [14].

If one has quantum dots magnetic beads conjugated target specific antibodies, such antibodies may be used to do the isolation and staining of specific cells from cell cultures, blood and bone marrow samples simultaneously. In this research, our goal was to develop and standardize a method, where one can do both steps in one single step. We used here CD27 B-Cells (plasma cells) as an example. Such methods can help to save time and money along opening new possibilities of automatic staining of cells.

Material and Methods

The human mononuclear cells were immunized with different targets in 2-3% FCS in RPMI as well as DMEM solutions containing 1% Streptopenicillin as well as 1% Glutamine. All cell culture products were from Biochrome, Germany. These cells were producing specific antibodies against the immunized targets [15]. They are tested with conventional ELISA as well as magnetic beads ELISA [16]. The cells were regularly checked under microscope and fed once a week with cell culture media as mentioned elsewhere. (Exact method will be explained in our future publication as this under preparation) Human mononuclear cells were prepared from buffy coat (Red cross blood bank, Germany), where the donor is given a number, so that one cannot identify this, therefore there is no need of research ethnic committee approval.

CD27 positive B cells isolation: Two different methods for isolation of CD27 B-cells were developed:

5 ml of cell cultures from the above said cells were collected in 15 ml tubes and centrifuged to get the pellet at the bottom. After that pellet was washed twice with PBS. To this pellet, 2 μ l of quantum dot magnetic beads antibody conjugate against CD27 (MICROBOOS Nanomedicine GmbH, Germany) with two different 510 and 700 nm wavelength each was added and kept for 10 minutes in dark with 2 to 3 times shaking in between. After that 5 ml PBS was added and they are put in magnetic rack for 3 minutes. The supernatant was

discarded and pellet was suspended in 100 μ l PBS. 1 μ l from suspension was put on a slide to get it dried. After that it was fixed in ethanol for 5 minutes and mounted with the mounting media. They were observed under fluorescent microscope (Zeiss, Germany). These methods take around 30 minutes to complete.

Alternatively, 5 ml of cell culture was added in 15 ml tube. To this, 2 μ l of quantum dot magnetic beads antibodies conjugate against CD27 was added and kept 10 minutes. They were put in the magnetic rack (Genekam, Germany). The supernatant was removed. The collected pellet was washed in 5 ml PBS twice, while suspending the pellet in 50 or 100 μ l PBS. The 2 μ l of pellet was put on a glass slide, dried, fixed with ethanol and mounted as mentioned above. This takes 30 minutes.

Observation of cells on the slides were done with different filters like UV, blue and green on the fluorescent microscopy with different magnifications with and without oil.

The observations of above cells were also tried with low priced fluorescent microscope (Biobase, China), but it was total failure.

These B-cells were further analyzed for the presence of antibody specific fragments with molecular methods. (The publication of this work is in process)

Results

To observe the stained cells, fluorescent microscope (Zeiss, Germany) was the right choice as this is an LED based microscope and 12 times expensive than that of the low-priced fluorescent microscope (Biobase, China). Therefore, all studies to observe the stained cells with quantum dots magnetic beads antibodies conjugates were done with fluorescent microscope (Zeiss, Germany).

We have conducted 10 experiments as example. Each experiment, there were successful isolation CD27 B-cells with both methods with quantum dots with two different wavelengths. There was no difference between the results of both isolation methods. There were sufficient number of cells to be observed under the microscope. (Picture 1) Under normal microscope without fluorescent function, magnetic beads isolated cells were observed. (Picture 2) The magnetic beads are attached on the surface of CD27 specific cells. Time needed for 2 step staining is around 60 minutes.

Even after 2 years of staining, the mounted slides are showing fluorescence without any reduction in intensity.

Table 1 shows the summary of the results of all experiments as 10 experiments, there was successful isolation of CD27 specific cells with magnetic beads and they emitted the specific fluorescence according to the wavelength of quantum dots. In the negative controls, there was no signal and no isolation.

We were unable to count the number of isolated cells under microscope in Neubauer chamber with trypan blue staining as they are in clumps as shown in the pictures.

Discussion

In this work, it is shown that there is successful use of quantum dots magnetic beads antibodies conjugate for isolation and staining of cells as one step in two different methods as mentioned under methods. The time needed for completion of mounted slide is 30 minutes. This is very fast method for finishing a fluorescent assay. At present, the two steps method is taking more than one hour time. As quantum dots staining can be kept for longtime against the conventional staining with FITC, which starts fading within an hour. This is another advantage of the method mentioned here. The slides can be stored for long time.

We observed that there is no different in two steps method and our one step method, hence we shifted the isolation and staining with the above said method for CD27 positive cells. Not only this, we are using similar type of the method for other B cells markers like CD19, CD20, CD38 etc too for conducting other experiments, which will be published later.

One must be very clear that the use of these quantum dots conjugated ligands need high quality microscope, which is expensive against low end fluorescent microscopes with mercury lamps. Such quantum dots magnetic beads conjugates are used to isolate CD27 B cells, hence this can help to enrich plasma cells for different applications e.g., gene therapy and molecular biological analysis. There are many B cell involving cancers; hence these results of this work may contribute to develop better diagnostics.

There are groups, which have developed similar type of methods as described in this work for other applications like development of immunoassays as well as methods used to test the presence of toxins in foods [17-20].

Another group has successfully developed similar method for circulating tumor cells from the blood samples to capture and stain these cells in one step, while they used these cells later on for immunochemistry, PCR and cell culturing, but this is rare report in literature [14, 21].

In another publication, we have shown that 2-3% FCS is sufficient to develop and maintain the mononuclear cells, in this work we used this [16].

This one step saves time, energy and money. Such one step methods also may open the doors to develop automatic robotic machines with artificial intelligence software for staining and analysis of slides from different cell cultures, which may accelerate the scientific immunological work.

In the literature, there is no report using quantum dots magnetic beads antibody conjugate to isolate the CD27 positive B-cells from immunized mononuclear cells, hence this should be considered the first report about isolation and staining of CD27 B-cells.

Our method mention opens new doors for new kinds of 3D applications for CD27 positive cells, which can be manipulated without any instruments through the magnetic field along with being observed under 3D fluorescent microscope.

Conclusion

This may be one first report in literature to isolate and stain the CD27 B cells with quantum dots magnetic beads antibody conjugate from mononuclear cell cultures for fluorescent

microscopy as one step method. This results in less 30 minutes and saves money against two step method being used today, which needs more time and sources. This method may like to improve the development of B cell applications in medicine.

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Picture 1 shows the isolated and stained CD27 positive plasma cells under the fluorescence microscope. The surface of these cells is emitting the fluorescence. (40X)

Picture 2 shows the isolated and stained CD27 positive plasma cells under microscope. The magnetic beads are attached on the surface of these cells. (40X)

Table 1 results of experiments for CD27 positive cells isolated with quantum dots magnetic beads antibody conjugate as single step.

Experiment number	Quantum dot emission wavelength (nm)	Florescence on CD27 positive cells	Magnetic beads on CD27 positive cells
1	510	+	+
2	510	+	+
3	510	+	+
4	510	+	+
5	510	+	+
6	700	+	+
7	700	+	+
8	700	+	+
9	700	+	+
10	700	+	+
11 (negative control)	510	-	-
12 (negative control)	700	-	-